

Minimum isolation distance for hybrid rice production

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In studies to determine the minimum isolation distance for maintaining male sterile lines and for producing genetically pure hybrid rice seed, Zhen Shan 97A, a cytoplasmic-genic male sterile (CMS) line, was used as the female parent and Zhen Shan 97B as the pollinator. Zhen Shan 97B seedlings were transplanted at 40 d after seeding (DAS) on 19 and 26 Jul 1986 in a 5- × 5-m block. Zhen Shan 97A was transplanted in 50-m-long single rows in directions related to normal prevailing winds during anthesis. Plant-to-plant distance was 50 cm. Seed set was recorded by distance from pollinator. Percentage seed set was computed as the ratio of seeds/plant to florets/plant.

Seed set on CMS plants near the

Seed set on cytoplasmic male sterile rice plants. Ludhiana, India.

Distance (m) from pollinator	Percent seed set of plants at given direction from pollinator							
1	1.73	2.07	2.28	2.01	1.90	2.81	1.80	
5	0.79	0.57	0.63	0.68	0.51	0.89	0.35	
10	0.31	0.00	0.38	0.35	0.42	0.34	0.00	
14	0.10	0.18	0.19	0.00	0.39	0.00	0.11	
15	0.13	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.18	0.14	—	
16	0.11	0.12	0.00	0.31	0.35	0.18	—	
17	—	—	0.11	0.16	0.29	0.12	—	
18	—	—	0.14	0.15	0.34	—	—	
19	—	—	0.00	—	0.00	—	—	
20	—	—	0.00	—	0.18	—	—	
21	—	—	0.00	—	0.11	—	—	
22	—	—	0.12	—	—	—	—	
50	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	

pollinator was high, but dropped drastically as distance from pollinator increased. No seed set occurred beyond 22 m in any direction (see table). The maximum coverage occurred when average wind velocity was 4 km/h, mean temperature was 27.5 °C, and relative humidity was 74% during Sep 1986.

These results suggest that rice pollen can disperse up to about 22 m under

those particular weather conditions. However, because pollen dispersal depends upon such factors as pollination vigor, wind direction, wind velocity, relative humidity, temperature, and hours of sunshine, confirmation over years and locations is needed to establish isolation distances for maintaining male sterile lines and for producing hybrid seed. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization TISSUE CULTURE

Tissue culture propagation of cytosterile stocks

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Somatic embryogenesis through formation of myriad supernumerary and adventitious embryoids in callus cultures is an attractive approach for mass propagation of the cytosterile stocks used in hybrid rice production. Cytosterile stocks (A lines) are maintained by pollination with fertile isonuclear maintainers (B lines).

For large-scale multiplication, A and B lines normally are grown in alternating rows in isolation. We have successfully used tissue culture techniques to mass-produce four cytosterile lines possessing WA

cytoplasm: V20A, Madhu A, IR48483A, and IR46830A.

Callus was initiated from dehusked sterilized seeds by culturing on N6 medium supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-dichlorophenoxy acetic acid (2,4-D) per liter. Each seed embryo yielded a 400-500 mg callus mass within 3-4 wk.

The 4-wk-old embryo-derived calluses were transferred to MS regeneration medium containing auxin (naphthalene acetic acid [NAA], 0.75 mg/ liter), cytokinins (kinetin, 0.25 mg/ liter), and benzyladenine (BA) (0.75 mg/liter) in the proportion 3:1:3. Very high frequency plantlet regeneration was obtained within 3 wk; 200-250 plantlets could be regenerated from the callus derived from a single seed (see figure).

With another passage in culture, the callus derived from a single seed can

Plantlets obtained from somatic callus cultured from a single seed.

give rise to a tenfold increase in mass, and 2,000-3,000 regenerated plantlets

can be expected from a single seed.

We also cultured another source of explant — young immature panicles (inflorescence) of the cytotsterile stocks — on MS, N₆, and H_e media supplemented with various growth regulators. Callus could be induced after 2 wk of culture from the surface of the spikelets, but the callus appeared to be mostly nonembryogenic.

For practical application of micropropagation techniques to mass production of special breeding stocks, such as cytotsteriles and the elite hybrids, three factors should be

considered: the time required for *in vitro* multiplication, the purity of the genotype in cultured and regenerated plants, and the capacity of regenerants to withstand the transfer from tube to soil. In our experience, within 8-9 wk the multiplication rate of stock as plantlets is 1:200. Rooting for better anchoring capacity and hardening the regenerated plants for transfer from tube to soil may need another 2 wk. Seedlings of transplantable size can be obtained in 11-12 wk.

We examined the regenerated plants for variants induced in callus culture (somaclonal variation). The

regenerants did not exhibit any variation in sterility or other morphological traits. However, our observations were limited to cultured plants obtained directly from embryo calluses without subculturing.

Callus proliferation through several passages of subculture, the level of 2,4-D in the induction medium, and the concentration of BA in the regeneration medium may induce variation in callus cultures. The purity of the genotype maintained in tissue culture multiplication efforts needs critical examination. □

Phenotypic patterns in somaclones from plants regenerated from somatic cell culture of IR lines

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Families of plants regenerated from somatic cell culture of IR36, IR50, IR52, and IR54 were evaluated in the second generation (Sc₂). Four groups were classified by phenotypic patterns and somaclone relationships to donor parents (Table 1): 1) no segregation within the family, similar to parent

type (SPT) (82.9%); 2) no segregation (uniform) within the family but dissimilar to parent type (DPT) (1.7%); 3) limited segregation involving one or two characters (simple segregation); and 4) more than two characters segregating simultaneously.

We found no significant differences in character between the SPTs and donor variety, but DPTs and the donor variety significantly differed in days from sowing to flowering, plant type, shape and color of leaves, length of flag leaf, plant height, effective tillers, length of panicles, seed numbers/panicle, and seed shape (Table 2). However, each DPT population was still uniform within the family. The coefficient of variation of all characters was less in the DPTs than in the donor variety, showing that the DPTs were homozygous. □

Table 1. Phenotypic patterns of the Sc₂ generation in somaclones of indica rice. ^a Guangzhou, China.

Sc ₂ lines derived from	Sc ₂ (no.) in given phenotypic pattern				Total (no.)
	No segregation		With segregation		
	Similar to donor parent	Dissimilar to donor parent	Simple segregation	Complex segregation	
IR36	99 (77.9)	5 (3.9)	7 (5.5)	16 (12.6)	127
IR50	2 (50.0)	0	1 (25)	1 (25)	4
IR52	2 (25.0)	0	0	6 (75.0)	8
IR54 ^b	136 (90.6)	0	11 (7.4)	3 (2.0)	150
Total	239 (82.9)	5 (4.7)	19 (6.3)	26 (9.1)	289

^a Values in parentheses are percentages. ^b Maturity of IR54 too late to evaluate characters, classified according to days from seeding to flowering.

Table 2. Agronomic characteristics of nonsegregating somaclones and donor variety. ^a Guangzhou, China.

Variety and somaclones ^b	Seeding to harvest (d)	Blade color ^c	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Effective panicles (no.)	Seeds/panicle (no.)	Seed setting (%)
IR36	118	L	71.1 ± 3.7	19.5 ± 2.4	18.0 ± 4.2	98.7 ± 22.1	81.6 ± 10.3
SPT	S1	L	68.4 ± 2.0	20.5 ± 2.1	14.1 ± 2.0*	128.1 ± 21.4**	80.3 ± 8.8
	S2	L	71.4 ± 3.2	20.9 ± 2.4*	15.1 ± 3.0*	116.8 ± 12.5**	82.4 ± 5.7
	S3	L	72.6 ± 4.2	19.6 ± 1.1	10.1 ± 2.7**	96.5 ± 15.8	79.9 ± 14.5
	S4	L	70.8 ± 4.6	22.6 ± 2.3*	15.7 ± 3.5	87.6 ± 4.8*	71.9 ± 8.8**
DPT	D1	D	59.4 ± 3.7**	20.4 ± 1.1	15.6 ± 3.2	78.5 ± 6.3***	86.4 ± 6.3*
	D2	D	52.8 ± 2.9**	16.1 ± 1.4**	15.1 ± 3.0*	68.8 ± 8.1**	78.8 ± 8.9
	D3	D	61.9 ± 3.7**	18.7 ± 2.5	11.0 ± 2.9**	76.9 ± 5.7**	83.1 ± 8.0
	D4	D	58.8 ± 3.1**	16.9 ± 1.7**	14.2 ± 2.9*	55.9 ± 6.4**	74.3 ± 10.8*
	D5	D	59.9 ± 2.0**	17.8 ± 1.4**	10.6 ± 3.7**	66.8 ± 5.5**	83.8 ± 7.9

^a *Significantly different from the donor parent variety at 0.05 level. **Significantly different from the donor parent variety at 0.01 level. ^b SPT = similar to donor parent variety, DPT = dissimilar to donor parent variety. ^c L = light color, D = dark color.